

THE IMPORTANCE OF STATE ADMINISTRATION IN THE FIELD OF CULTURE AND ART IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article talks about the reforms being carried out in the field of culture and art in New Uzbekistan, their effectiveness and the high attention paid by our state.

Key words: art, culture, management, practice, theory, society, production, improvement.

Each nation will be known and famous for its national value, culture and art. Let's not bring any country to our eyes, we will embody it in front of our eyes with national clothes, works of art and culture. In particular, we are embodied in the imagination of foreign peoples first of all with our art and culture, nationality, and music.

It is no secret to all of us that special attention is paid to the field of culture and art in our country, where new technologies are developing day by day.

In today's rapidly developing era, the concept of "New Uzbekistan" put forward by the head of our state has sounded in the language of our people in a unique way and encourages to take a step towards a new outlook and thinking.

A number of laws as well as decisions and decrees were adopted in the field of culture and art in a manner worthy of the public. In particular, in order to further develop and improve the field, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 26, 2018 "On innovative development of the culture and art sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and on May 26, 2020 "Culture and art Decree No. PF-6000 [1.470-478] on measures to further increase the role and influence of the field of culture in the life of society was adopted. In addition, on December 9, 2021, the PQ-36 [2:www.lex.uz] "On further improvement of the system of support for the development of horse" and on February 2, 2022 "On the further development of the sphere of culture and art" "On additional measures" No. PQ-112[3:1]

Honorable President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 2017 meeting with the employees of the culture and art sector: "We should never forget one fact: if culture and art do not develop in our country, society will not develop. The level of development of our people is evaluated primarily according to our national culture. In this sense, culture is the image of our nation and society. "Since we are starting to create a new image of Uzbekistan, we should start with the development of our national culture." Indeed, raising the level and knowledge of the people, and the standard of living, first of all, begins with the further improvement of culture. The place and value of a state with a developed society and an appreciated culture also occupies high places. Only if attention is paid seriously to the field, if the officials approach their work responsibly and if new innovations are implemented using foreign experiences, it will be appropriate and will be implemented in accordance with the intended goals. if we look at the analysis:

In particular, the official websites, online platforms of the universities of culture and art of the United Kingdom, the United States of America, Japan, the name of the relevant course, how to start the study, its duration, the number of students, places of examination, levels of educational specialists, methods of monitoring and controlling the educational process, types of the educational process, criteria for evaluating the educational process, the content and duration of the educational process have been analyzed by many foreign countries and applied in practice not done.

The work carried out in our country in the direction of the development of culture and art is extremely consistent with the priority measures aimed at ensuring spiritual development and bringing the industry to a new level reflected in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan. We can say that these reforms will contribute to the practical realization of the idea "From the strategy of actions - to the strategy of development" based on the principle of goodness and humanity, to the realization of the concept of "New Uzbekistan - an enlightened society". Each nation occupies a strong place in world civilization with the power of its culture and art. The development of this sector is one of the important factors that show the strength and potential of the country, the value of the people, its reputation and status in the world.

Currently, in the newly developed "Strategy of Development", a separate section is allocated to the spiritual and educational sphere and the inclusion of a work plan in the sphere of culture and art during 2022-2026 is an example of high attention directed to the sphere. . For us, spirituality is a complex of exemplary qualities, mutual trust, respect and attention between people, noble aspirations to jointly build the future of the nation and the state. In other words, spirituality is the foundation that determines the content and quality of all political and social relations in society. Above, we have given a number of examples of the high level of attention and care paid to the industry today. Extensive work is being carried out within the framework of measures for the development of such a field, as well as high attention and ensuring the execution of signed decrees and decisions. It would not be wrong to say that the care and opportunities given to the industry by the head of our state will lead to radical changes in the near future and will bear fruit.

Feeling such high attention and trust, young experts and industry workers like us should work more enthusiastically and mobilize all their strength and potential for the development of culture and art. Therefore, as the Honorable President noted, "New Uzbekistan will become a strong, potential, well-respected, prosperous and prosperous country in the world."

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Cultural Activities and Cultural Organizations" adopted by the Legislative Chamber and approved by the Senate on January 6, 2021 regulates cultural activities, relations in the field of cultural organizations, the creator, the creative community , is extremely important in terms of supporting creative activity. Cultural and public events in our country, concerts and performances, folk art, folk games, activities of cultural centers, national cultural centers, strengthening of cooperation in the field of cultural activities, popularization of cultural objects and works of art, development of culture in remote areas, social protection of cultural workers is a program in terms of As an example of the high attention paid to the field and its representatives, we can see that April 15 is designated as the "Day of Culture Workers". It is not an exaggeration to say that on the eve of this joyful day, the establishment of the "Artists' Garden" at Nurabad Fortress, the educational center of Ohangaron district of Tashkent region, on the initiative of the Ministry of Culture, was like a wedding. This reality, which had never been observed before, pleased the workers

of the field. [4:6] This historical reality was welcomed and rejoiced by the workers of the field. It is not wrong to say that it motivated them to fulfill their duties more seriously. The above-mentioned Presidential Decree No. PQ-112 "On additional measures for the further development of the sphere of culture and art" involves attracting young people to cultural centers, holding contests, festivals, set priorities such as identifying talented young people, supporting creative young people, increasing the level of providing cultural recreation services to the population, especially citizens living in remote areas.

Within the framework of such decisions and projects, a lot of work has been carried out. These reforms will be further developed based on the principles of goodness and humanity, using foreign experience, and expanding the scope of new innovations.

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